
ABSTRACT

This research work puts into application the regression equation derived by Ibearugbulem for a four component mixture of concrete to develop a model for the easy forecast of 28th day flexural strengths. To ensure an accurate forecast, the mix ratios to be predicted must fall within the boundaries defined for a four component simplex latex structure. The materials used in the laboratory experiment include; water, Ordinary Portland Cement, river sand, river gravel, and periwinkle shells. River gravel and periwinkle shells were combined at a volumetric mix ratio of 1:1 thereby reducing the number of material components from five to four. Manual mixing operation was adopted while all concrete ingredients except for the coarse aggregates were batched by weight. A total of 30 mix ratios were utilised in the concreting operation. While the first 15 mix ratios were used in the formulation of the model, the last 15 mix ratios were used in the validation of the formulated model using fisher's statistical test. Three concrete beams were cast for each mix ratio of which a total of 90 prototype beams measuring 150x150x600mm were produced and cured for 28 days in an open curing tank filled with potable water. From the statistical analysis, the calculated f-value 1.05 was less than the allowable f-value of 2.48 obtained from statistical table at 95% confidence level. This shows that the difference between the laboratory and model flexural strength results is not significant. Therefore, the formulated model is adequate and reliable for predicting the 28th day flexural strengths of periwinkle shell-river gravel concrete when given mix ratios.

KEYWORDS: Flexural strength, Periwinkle shell-river gravel concrete, Mix ratio, Regression model

INTRODUCTION

Concrete is one of the major building materials in civil engineering practice and construction works in Nigeria. Its basic constituents are cement, fine aggregates, coarse aggregate and water. Therefore, the overall cost of concrete production depends on the availability of these constituent materials. The conventional normal weight coarse aggregates needed for construction purposes are expensive hence the need to source for suitable and more readily available alternative construction materials.

Periwinkle shell obtained from periwinkle, which is an available proteinous food to people living in riverine and coastal communities in Nigeria, has been investigated by several researchers as a coarse aggregate for lightweight concrete production. Adewuyi and Adegoke (2009), Amaziah et al. (2013), Awe et al. (2014), Elijah et al. (2009), Ettu et al. (2013), Falade et al. (2010), Njoku et al. (2011), Ohimain et al. (2009), and Osarenwinda and Awaro (2009) have all carried out series of investigations on the prospects of using periwinkle shells, which were regarded as pollutants due to their unsightly appearance in open-dump sites as partial replacement for the unavailable and expensive conventional normal weight coarse aggregates in lightweight concrete production. These researchers having combined periwinkle shells at different partial replacements with the conventional normal weight coarse aggregate proved it to be adequate for lightweight concrete production.

Another factor which could increase the cost of production of concrete is the enormous time and effort invested in carrying-out trial mixes for desired fresh or hardened concrete properties. To overcome this short coming, Ibearugbulem et al. (2013), Osadebe (2003) and Scheffe(1950) have all developed optimisation equations for the prediction of compressive and flexural strengths of concretes and sandcrete/lateritic blocks.

This research work therefore seeks to apply the regression equation developed by Ibearugbulem for a four component mixture to formulate a new model for the prediction of the 28th day flexural strengths of periwinkle shell-river gravel concrete. The objective of this research if realised will help equip civil engineers working in concrete or construction industries with easy to use mathematical tool for predicting flexural strengths of lightweight concrete, thereby saving the enormous time and effort invested in carrying out trial mixes. It will also help manage the enormous pollution generated by periwinkle shell through their use as a construction material for lightweight concrete production.

IBEARUGBULEM’S REGRESSION MODEL

Ibearugbulem et al. (2013) derived a regression equation for a four component mixture of concrete of degree four given in Equation 1. This equation forms the basis of the regression model developed in this research for the prediction of flexural strength of lightweight concrete having equal volume of periwinkle shells and river gravel.

$$F(z) = \alpha_1 z_1 + \alpha_2 z_2 + \alpha_3 z_3 + \alpha_4 z_4 + \alpha_{12} z_1 z_2 + \alpha_{13} z_1 z_3 + \alpha_{14} z_1 z_4 + \alpha_{23} z_2 z_3 + \alpha_{24} z_2 z_4 + \alpha_{34} z_3 z_4 + \alpha_{123} z_1 z_2 z_3 + \alpha_{124} z_1 z_2 z_4 + \alpha_{134} z_1 z_3 z_4 + \alpha_{234} z_2 z_3 z_4 + \alpha_{1234} z_1 z_2 z_3 z_4 \tag{1}$$

Where, F(z) is the response function (i.e the property of concrete that is of interest).

α is the coefficient of the regression equation obtained from Equation 4.

Z is the pseudo variable obtained from Equations 2 and 3.

PSEUDO AND ACTUAL VARIABLES

The relationship between the pseudo variable, z_i and actual variable, s_i is as given below.

$$z_i = s_i / S \tag{2}$$

$$S = \sum s_i \tag{3}$$

COEFFICIENT OF THE REGRESSION FUNCTION

The matrix expression below given by Ibearugbulem is used to obtain the coefficient of the regression function.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sum_r z_1 \cdot F(z) \\ \sum_r z_2 \cdot F(z) \\ \sum_r z_3 \cdot F(z) \\ \vdots \\ \sum_r z_1 z_2 z_3 \dots F(z) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sum_r z_1 z_1 & \sum_r z_2 z_1 & \sum_r z_3 z_1 & \dots & \dots \\ \sum_r z_1 z_2 & \sum_r z_2 z_2 & \sum_r z_3 z_2 & \dots & \dots \\ \sum_r z_1 z_3 & \sum_r z_2 z_3 & \sum_r z_3 z_3 & \dots & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sum_r z_1 z_1 z_2 & \dots & \sum_r z_2 z_1 z_2 & \dots & \dots \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha_{123\dots} \end{pmatrix} \tag{4}$$

Equation 4 can be written in a short form as shown in Equation 5.

$$[F(z) \cdot Z] = [CC][\alpha] \tag{5}$$

Where, CC is always a symmetric matrix. For a mixture of four components, CC is a 15x15 matrix shown in Table 2. Making $[\alpha]$ the subject of the gives Equation 6.

$$[\alpha] = [F(z) \cdot Z] \cdot [CC]^{-1} \tag{6}$$

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Five constituent materials were used in the laboratory to produce the prototype concrete beams measuring 150x150x600mm. These materials include Ordinary Portland cement, river sand, river gravel, periwinkle shell and water.

- (i) The Ordinary Portland cement with properties conforming to BS EN 197-1:2000 was used in the laboratory experiment.
- (ii) The river sand used was obtained from Otamiri River located in federal university of technology owerri. It has physical properties of 1670kg/m³, 0.36, 2.608 and 2.52 corresponding to its values of un-compacted bulk density, void ratio, specific gravity and fineness modulus respectively. The river sand is uniformly graded because it has coefficient of uniformity and coefficient of curvature values of 2.32 and 0.87 respectively obtained from Figure 1.
- (iii) The river gravel used in the experiment has a maximum size of 20mm and rounded in shape. It has an un-compacted bulk density, water absorption, void ratio, specific gravity, fineness modulus, impact value and abrasion value of 1588kg/m³, 0.8%, 0.42, 2.718, 8.02, 21.49% and 41.58% respectively. The river gravel is poorly graded because of its values of coefficient of uniformity and curvature which are 1.39 and 1.14 respectively obtained from Figure 2.
- (iv) The periwinkle shells which have a maximum size of 19mm were obtained from Rumuagholu market in River state. It has physical and mechanical properties of 520kg/m³, 2.4%, 0.55, 1.16, 3.72, 33.50% and 55.04% which corresponds to the un-compacted bulk density, water absorption, void ratio, specific gravity, fineness modulus, impact value and abrasion value respectively. Its coefficient of uniformity and curvature values of 1.18 and 1.12 obtained from Figure 3 indicate a poorly graded particle.
- (v) Potable water was used for the experiment during mixing and curing operation.

METHODS

CONCRETE MATERIALS BATCHING, MIXING, PLACING AND CURING OPERATIONS

Batching in this experiment was done with a weighing balance of 50kg capacity using the mix ratios given in Table 1. These mix ratios were chosen arbitrarily from Scheffe's simplex latex structure for a four component mixture. The batching for the different constituent materials was by mass except for the coarse aggregates (i.e river gravel and periwinkle shells) which were volumetrically combined at a mix ratio of 1:1.

TABLE 1: ACTUAL MIX RATIOS

S/N	OBSERVATION POINTS	WATER, _{s1}	CEMENT, _{s2}	SAND, _{s3}	COARSE AGGREGATE, _{s4}
1	N1	0.6	1	2	4
2	N2	0.55	1	2	3
3	N3	0.5	1	1.5	2
4	N4	0.45	1	1	1.5
5	N12	0.575	1	2	3.5
6	N13	0.55	1	1.75	3
7	N14	0.525	1	1.5	2.75
8	N23	0.525	1	1.75	2.5
9	N24	0.5	1	1.5	2.25
10	N34	0.475	1	1.25	1.75
11	N123	0.55	1	1.8333	3
12	N124	0.533333	1	1.6667	2.8333
13	N134	0.516667	1	1.5	2.5
14	N234	0.5	1	1.5	2.1667
15	N1234	0.525	1	1.675	2.625
16	C1	0.5175	1	1.575	2.475
17	C2	0.5275	1	1.675	2.65
18	C3	0.5375	1	1.7	2.85
19	C4	0.5175	1	1.55	2.525
20	C5	0.521	1	1.575	2.565
21	C6	0.4985	1	1.485	2.16
22	C7	0.5215	1	1.54	2.565
23	C8	0.5285	1	1.65	2.745
24	C9	0.5515	1	1.825	3.03

25	C10	0.5045	1	1.545	2.21
26	C11	0.585	1	2	3.7
27	C12	0.535	1	1.85	2.7
28	C13	0.485	1	1.35	1.85
29	C14	0.495	1	1.3	2.25
30	C15	0.5325	1	1.6625	2.65
30	C15	0.5325	1	1.6625	2.65

Manual mixing was adopted with the aid of spade. The constituent materials were mixed thoroughly until homogeneity was attained. After mixing, the concrete was cast into steel moulds measuring 150x150x600mm.

Three representative samples were cast for each mix ratio, making a total of 90 prototype concrete beams produced. They were cured for 28 days in an open curing tank filled with potable water. 100kN capacity hand operated flexural testing machined designed for third point loading was used to crush the cured concrete beams. Constant rate of loading was applied on the concrete beams until failure occurred. The laboratory modulus of rupture or flexural strength of each beam was determined using Equation 7. The results obtained are given on Table 3.

$$\text{Flexural strength} = \frac{\text{load on beam} \times \text{span}}{6 \times \text{elastic modulus of beam}} \quad (7)$$

GOODNESS OF FIT

Fisher's test is used to test the adequacy of the model by comparing the properties (flexural strengths) of the "control samples" of the experiment with that of the model. The values obtained from the model is said to be adequate if

$$\frac{1}{f_{\alpha}(v_1, v_2)} < \frac{s_1^2}{s_2^2} < f_{\alpha}(v_1, v_2) .$$

Where,

$\frac{s_1^2}{s_2^2}$ = fisher value obtained from statistical analysis

s_1^2 = greater of S_E^2 and S_m^2

S_m^2 = variance from the model

S_E^2 = variance from the experiment

$f_{\alpha}(v_1, v_2)$ = fisher value obtained from F- distribution table.

α = significant level = 5% = 0.05

$V_1 = V_2 = N-1$ = degree of freedom.

TABLE 2:CC Matrix of a Mix of Four Components

$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z2	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z2 Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_1$ Z2Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_1$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_1$ Z2Z3Z4
$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2$ Z2	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2$ Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z2	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2$ Z2Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2Z_2$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z2 Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z2Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2Z_2$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z2Z3Z4
$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2$ Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_3$ Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_3$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z3Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2$ Z3Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2Z_3$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_3$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z3 Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_3$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2Z_3$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z3Z3Z4
$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_3$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_4$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z4Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2Z_4$ Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_3$ Z4Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z3 Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z4Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_3$ Z4Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_2Z_3$ Z4Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z3Z4Z4
$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z2	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z2	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z2 Z2	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z2 Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z2 Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z2 Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z2Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z3 Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z2 Z2Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_1$ Z2Z2Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_1$ Z2Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z2Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_1$ Z2Z2Z3 Z4
$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z3Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z2 Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z3 Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z3 Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z2Z3 Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z3Z3 Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1$ Z1Z2 Z3Z3	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_1$ Z2Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_1$ Z3Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_2$ Z3Z3Z4	$\Sigma\Sigma Z_1Z_1$ Z2Z3Z3 Z4
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ΣΣΖ1 ΖΖΖ3	ΣΣΖ2 ΖΖΖ3	ΣΣΖ2 ΖΖΖ3	ΣΣΖ2 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1 ΖΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3	ΣΣΖ1 ΖΖΖ3	ΣΣΖ1 ΖΖΖ3 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ2 ΖΖΖ3	ΣΣΖ2ΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ2 ΖΖΖ3 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1 ΖΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3	ΣΣΖ1ΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3ΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1ΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3ΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ2ΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3ΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1ΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3ΖΖ3
ΣΣΖ1 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ2 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ2 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ2 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1 ΖΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1 ΖΖΖ3 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1 ΖΖΖ3 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ2 ΖΖΖ3 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ2ΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ2 ΖΖΖ3 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1 ΖΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3 ΖΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1ΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3ΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1ΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3ΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ2ΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3ΖΖ4	ΣΣΖ1ΖΖ2 ΖΖΖ3ΖΖ4
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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

GRAIN SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF RIVER SAND, RIVER GRAVEL AND PERIWINKLE SHELLS

Figures 1, 2 and 3 represent the grain size distribution of river sand, river gravel and periwinkle shells used in the laboratory experiment.

Figure 1: Grain size distribution analysis for river sand

Figure 2: Grain size distribution analysis for a river gravel

Figure 3: Grain size distribution of periwinkle shells

LABORATORY FLEXURAL STRENGTHS

Table 3: Laboratory Flexural Strengths of Periwinkle shell-River gravel concrete

ACTUAL MIX RATIOS															
MIX NO	N1	N2	N3	N4	N12	N13	N14	N23	N24	N34	N123	N124	N134	N234	N1234
AVERAGE FLEXURAL STRENGTH (N/mm ²)	3.5	3.32	3.54	3.72	2.8	2.69	2.65	2.17	3.04	3.27	2.69	2.5	2.78	2.52	2.6
CONTROL MIX RATIOS															
MIX NO	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15
AVERAGE FLEXURAL STRENGTH (N/mm ²)	2.77	2.47	2.24	2.75	2.9	2.65	3.07	3.04	3.29	2.77	3.12	3.02	3.13	3.09	3.15

FLEXURAL STRENGTH FROM FORMULATED REGRESSION MODEL

PSEUDO VARIABLES, Z_i

The pseudo variable values given in Table 4 are obtained using Table 1 and Equations 2 and 3.

TABLE 4: PSEUDO VARIABLES (Z_i)														
Z1	Z2	Z3	Z4	Z1Z2	Z1Z3	Z1Z4	Z2Z3	Z2Z4	Z3Z4	Z1Z2Z3	Z1Z2Z4	Z1Z3Z4	Z2Z3Z4	Z1Z2Z3Z4
0.079	0.132	0.263	0.526	0.010	0.021	0.042	0.035	0.069	0.139	0.003	0.005	0.011	0.018	0.001
0.0	0.1	0.30	0.45	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.07	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00

84	53	5	8	3	6	8	7	0	0	4	6	2	1	2
0.100	0.200	0.300	0.400	0.020	0.030	0.040	0.060	0.080	0.120	0.006	0.008	0.012	0.024	0.002
0.114	0.253	0.253	0.380	0.029	0.029	0.043	0.064	0.096	0.096	0.007	0.011	0.011	0.024	0.003
0.081	0.141	0.283	0.495	0.011	0.023	0.040	0.040	0.070	0.140	0.003	0.006	0.011	0.020	0.002
0.087	0.159	0.278	0.476	0.014	0.024	0.042	0.044	0.076	0.132	0.004	0.007	0.012	0.021	0.002
0.091	0.173	0.260	0.476	0.016	0.024	0.043	0.045	0.082	0.124	0.004	0.008	0.011	0.021	0.002
0.091	0.173	0.303	0.433	0.016	0.028	0.039	0.052	0.075	0.131	0.005	0.007	0.012	0.023	0.002
0.095	0.190	0.286	0.429	0.018	0.027	0.041	0.054	0.082	0.122	0.005	0.008	0.012	0.023	0.002
0.106	0.223	0.279	0.391	0.024	0.030	0.042	0.062	0.087	0.109	0.007	0.009	0.012	0.024	0.003
0.086	0.157	0.287	0.470	0.013	0.025	0.040	0.045	0.074	0.135	0.004	0.006	0.012	0.021	0.002
0.088	0.166	0.276	0.470	0.015	0.024	0.042	0.046	0.078	0.130	0.004	0.007	0.011	0.022	0.002
0.094	0.181	0.272	0.453	0.017	0.025	0.042	0.049	0.082	0.123	0.005	0.008	0.012	0.022	0.002
0.097	0.194	0.290	0.419	0.019	0.028	0.041	0.056	0.081	0.122	0.005	0.008	0.012	0.024	0.002
0.091	0.173	0.281	0.455	0.016	0.026	0.041	0.059	0.079	0.128	0.004	0.007	0.012	0.022	0.002
0.093	0.180	0.283	0.445	0.017	0.026	0.041	0.051	0.080	0.126	0.005	0.007	0.012	0.023	0.002
0.090	0.171	0.286	0.453	0.015	0.026	0.041	0.059	0.077	0.130	0.004	0.007	0.012	0.022	0.002
0.088	0.164	0.279	0.468	0.015	0.025	0.041	0.056	0.077	0.131	0.004	0.007	0.012	0.021	0.002
0.093	0.179	0.277	0.452	0.017	0.026	0.042	0.050	0.081	0.125	0.005	0.007	0.012	0.022	0.002
0.092	0.177	0.278	0.453	0.016	0.026	0.042	0.059	0.080	0.126	0.005	0.007	0.012	0.022	0.002
0.097	0.194	0.289	0.420	0.019	0.028	0.041	0.056	0.082	0.122	0.005	0.008	0.012	0.024	0.002
0.093	0.178	0.274	0.456	0.016	0.025	0.042	0.059	0.081	0.125	0.005	0.008	0.012	0.022	0.002
0.089	0.169	0.279	0.463	0.015	0.025	0.042	0.057	0.078	0.129	0.004	0.007	0.012	0.022	0.002
0.086	0.156	0.285	0.473	0.013	0.025	0.042	0.054	0.074	0.135	0.004	0.006	0.012	0.021	0.002
0.096	0.190	0.294	0.420	0.018	0.028	0.040	0.056	0.080	0.123	0.005	0.008	0.012	0.023	0.002
0.080	0.137	0.275	0.508	0.012	0.022	0.041	0.038	0.070	0.139	0.003	0.006	0.011	0.019	0.002
0.088	0.164	0.304	0.444	0.014	0.027	0.039	0.050	0.073	0.135	0.004	0.006	0.012	0.022	0.002
0.104	0.213	0.288	0.395	0.022	0.030	0.041	0.062	0.084	0.114	0.006	0.009	0.012	0.024	0.003
0.098	0.198	0.258	0.446	0.019	0.025	0.042	0.051	0.088	0.115	0.005	0.009	0.011	0.023	0.002
0.091	0.171	0.284	0.453	0.016	0.026	0.042	0.059	0.079	0.128	0.004	0.007	0.012	0.022	0.002

CC MATRIX

Substituting the values of Table 4 into Table 2, the numeric values of CC matrix is obtained as given in Table 5. The inverse of it is given in Table 6.

Table 5: CC MATRIX

0.12 9	0.250	0.38 9	0.616	0.024	0.036	0.057	0.070	0.110	0.173	0.007	0.010	0.016	0.031	0.003
0.12 9	0.488	0.74 9	1.181	0.047	0.070	0.110	0.137	0.213	0.331	0.013	0.020	0.031	0.060	0.006
0.38 9	0.749	1.18 9	1.891	0.070	0.109	0.173	0.211	0.331	0.533	0.020	0.031	0.049	0.093	0.009
0.61 6	1.181	1.89 1	3.042	0.110	0.173	0.277	0.331	0.527	0.854	0.031	0.049	0.078	0.148	0.014
0.02 4	0.047	0.07 0	0.110	0.004	0.007	0.010	0.013	0.020	0.031	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.006	0.001
0.03 6	0.070	0.11 0	0.173	0.007	0.010	0.016	0.020	0.031	0.049	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.009	0.001
0.05 7	0.110	0.17 3	0.277	0.010	0.016	0.025	0.031	0.049	0.078	0.003	0.005	0.007	0.014	0.001
0.07 0	0.137	0.21 1	0.331	0.013	0.020	0.031	0.038	0.060	0.093	0.004	0.006	0.009	0.017	0.002
0.11 0	0.213	0.33 1	0.527	0.020	0.031	0.049	0.060	0.094	0.148	0.006	0.009	0.014	0.026	0.002
0.17 3	0.331	0.53 3	0.854	0.031	0.049	0.078	0.093	0.148	0.240	0.009	0.014	0.022	0.042	0.004
0.00 7	0.013	0.02 0	0.031	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.006	0.009	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.000
0.01 0	0.020	0.03 1	0.049	0.002	0.003	0.005	0.006	0.009	0.014	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.000
0.01 6	0.031	0.04 9	0.078	0.003	0.004	0.007	0.009	0.014	0.022	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.004	0.000
0.03 1	0.060	0.09 3	0.148	0.006	0.009	0.014	0.017	0.026	0.042	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.007	0.001
0.00 3	0.006	0.00 9	0.014	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000

Table 6: INVERSE OF CC MATRIX

89.5 8244	- 8.23 989	19.0674	- 13.96 19	- 69.80 66	- 498.2 13	209.9 039	111.5 498	- 43.82 96	6.033 514	117.3 796	- 267.6 88	- 157.1 64	- 12.64 37	88.1 4253
5844 471	68.5 698 5	1087359	- 11782 26	- 61500 15	- 3.40E +07	17337 558	92049 05	- 29863 36	11248 62	19115 33	- 2.50E +07	- 1.20E +07	- 54024 20	6118 754
- 1527 327	- 22.7 285	-375557	47024 2.1	16732 59	11953 464	- 72919 01	- 36289 74	90046 5	- 52784 6	- 13618 64	98730 48	38627 33	30661 23	- 1946 844
5928 941	79.0 082 2	1456552	- 14165 26	- 60654 59	- 4.10E +07	22828 587	10525 356	- 41335 13	11422 19	57405 19	- 2.90E +07	- 1.50E +07	- 46225 20	7820 639
5376 7678	132 9.34	- 4186093	- 34800 770	- 1.30E	- 4.46E +08	- 6.20E	- 3.09E	10807 450	- 6.70E	4.13E +08	8.65E +08	2.14E +08	4.23E +08	- 1.00

	9			+08		+08	+08		+07					E+0 8
3.21 E+0 8	482 7.16	4302254 2	- 42561 0	- 4.20E +08	- 7.60E +08	- 1.40E +08	- 9.5E+ 07	- 1.08E +08	- 5.10E +07	7.52E +08	56700 490	- 3.40E +08	4.48E +08	2.17 E+0 8
- 4.50 E+0 7	105 6.32 9	- 2.50E+0 7	- 80775 691	- 3.60E +07	1.36E +09	- 1.30E +09	- 6.86E +08	60000 075	- 1.40E +08	5.97E +08	1.85E +09	6.43E +08	8.46E +08	- 2.40 E+0 8
- 2.10 E+0 8	- 374 7.97	- 2.00E+0 7	- 2.80E +07	3.00E +08	48211 406	5.60E +08	3.09E +08	57984 921	83903 944	- 7.40E +08	- 7.00E +08	75980 47	- 6.30E +08	- 6.10 E+0 7
- 1.30 E+0 7	- 153 3.1	3036311	- 4.50E +07	6.60E +07	- 5.80E +08	7.16E +08	3.92E +08	25740 08	92788 837	- 4.90E +08	- 1.10E +09	- 3.40E +08	- 5.80E +08	9321 2128
- 5658 244	- 191. 912	- 1828362	- 19689 85	1.00E +07	22114 66	27550 727	18229 502	58189 00	68853 61	- 4.50E +07	- 5.90E +07	- 1.50E +07	- 4.00E +07	5812 754
2.29 E+0 8	898 2.95	- 3833674	2.07E +08	4.70E +08	2.52E +09	- 3.40E +09	- 1.91E +09	- 1.7E+ 07	- 4.40E +08	2.53E +09	4.67E +09	1.21E +09	2.90E +09	- 3.50 E+0 8
- 1.70 E+0 8	180 5.59 2	1174803 6	64757 954	2.30E +08	7.98E +08	- 7.30E +08	- 5.55E +08	- 7.4E+ 07	- 1.70E +08	7.01E +08	1.53E +09	7.35E +08	9.56E +08	7.70 E+0 7
- 6.90 E+0 8	- 150 55.6	- 3.40E+0 7	- 2.20E +08	1.10E +09	- 1.90E +09	4.02E +09	2.14E +09	1.06E +08	5.10E +08	- 3.50E +09	- 5.20E +09	- 8.80E +08	- 3.50E +09	2756 4092
4.21 E+0 8	135 40.2 3	1516349 8	2.68E +08	- 8.60E +08	2.86E +09	- 4.50E +09	- 2.46E +09	- 8.2E+ 07	- 5.90E +08	3.63E +09	6.42E +09	1.62E +09	3.84E +09	- 4.10 E+0 8
1.27 E+0 8	- 389 12.6	1.10E+0 8	- 1.40E +09	1.30E +09	- 1.90E +10	2.16E +10	1.19E +10	- 1.61E +08	2.85E +09	- 1.40E +10	- 3.20E +10	- 1.10E +10	- 1.70E +10	3.73 E+0 9

RZ VECTOR

RZ vector is defined as the matrix product of the response function ® on Table 3 and the pseudo variables (z) on Table 4. The result is as presented below.

$\Sigma(Z1.F(z))$	4.063473
$\Sigma(Z2.F(z))$	7.862
$\Sigma(Z3.F(z))$	12.287505
$\Sigma(Z4.F(z))$	19.577023
$\Sigma(Z1Z2.F(z))$	0.743303
$\Sigma(Z1Z3.F(z))$	1.138644
$\Sigma(Z1Z4.F(z))$	1.800394
$\Sigma(Z2Z3.F(z))$	2.20069
$\Sigma(Z2Z4.F(z))$	3.459767
$\Sigma(Z3Z4.F(z))$	5.490081
$\Sigma(Z1Z2Z3.F(z))$	0.207623
$\Sigma(Z1Z2Z4.F(z))$	0.324026
$\Sigma(Z1Z3Z4.F(z))$	0.50437
$\Sigma(Z2Z3Z4.F(z))$	0.968467
$\Sigma(Z1Z2Z3Z4.F(z))$	0.0905437

COEFFICIENTS OF THE REEGRESSION EQUATION

The coefficients of the regression equation given in Equation 1 can be obtained using Equation 6. That is, the coefficients of the regression equation are the matrix product of the RZ vector and the inverse of the CC matrix given on Table 6. The result is as given in Table 7.

α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_{12}	α_{13}	α_{14}	α_{23}	α_{24}	α_{34}	α_{123}	α_{124}	α_{134}	α_{234}	α_{1234}
0	146	55.	172	7441.	4582.	1328	6905.	7183.	405.	3604	4272.	46729.	48935.	232975
	.41	2	.6	25	69	3.4	69	75	19	7.5	23	42	93	.54

Substituting the coefficients in Table 7 into Equation 1 will give the regression model for the prediction of 28th day flexural strengths of periwinkle shell-river gravel concrete given in Equation 8.

$$F(z) = -464.49z_2 + 55.20z_3 - 172.60z_4 + 7441.25z_1z_2 + 4582.69z_1z_3 + 1328.40z_1z_4 - 6905.69z_2z_3 - 7183.75z_2z_4 - 405.19z_3z_4 + 3604.75z_1z_2z_3 + 4272.23z_1z_2z_4 - 46729.42z_1z_3z_4 + 48935.93z_2z_3z_4 - 232975.54z_1z_2z_3z_4 \quad (8)$$

The flexural strengths from the formulated model given in Table 8 are obtained through substitution of the pseudo variables in Table 4 into Equation 8. The flexural strengths from the model are placed side by side with that from the laboratory experiment for easy comparison and statistical analysis as represented on Table 9.

ACTUAL MIX RATIOS																
MIX NO		N1	N2	N3	N4	N12	N13	N14	N23	N24	N34	N123	N124	N134	N234	N1234
AVERAGE FLEXURAL STRENGTH (N/mm ²)	YMODEL	3.56	2.74	3.13	3.79	2.57	2.92	2.45	2.95	2.75	3.31	2.79	3.06	2.19	2.82	2.77
	YEXP	3.50	3.32	3.54	3.72	2.80	2.69	2.65	2.17	3.04	3.27	2.69	2.50	2.78	2.52	2.60
CONTROL MIX RATIOS																
MIX NO		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15
AVERAGE FLEXURAL STRENGTH (N/mm ²)	YMODEL	2.58	2.90	2.99	2.51	2.58	2.76	2.39	3.00	2.82	2.91	2.83	2.98	3.31	3.44	2.53
	YEXP	2.77	2.47	2.24	2.75	2.90	2.65	3.07	3.04	3.29	2.77	3.12	3.02	3.13	3.09	3.15

FISHER TEST FOR ADEQUACY OF MODEL

LEGEND

Y_E = response from experiment

Y_M = response from model

$\bar{Y}_E$ = mean response from experiment = $\sum Y_E/N$

$\bar{Y}_M$ = mean response from model = $\sum Y_M/N$

N = total points of observation (for controls) = 15

$S_E^2 = \sum (Y_E - \bar{Y}_E)^2 / (N-1)$

$S_M^2 = \sum (Y_M - \bar{Y}_M)^2 / (N-1)$

(N-1) = degree of freedom = 15-1 = 14

S_E^2 = variance from the experiment

S_M^2 = variance from the model

Table 9: Periwinkle Shell-River Gravel Concrete

MIX NO	Y_E	Y_M	$Y_E - \bar{Y}_E$	$Y_M - \bar{Y}_M$	$(Y_E - \bar{Y}_E)^2$	$(Y_M - \bar{Y}_M)^2$
C1	2.77	2.58	-0.13	-0.26	0.0169	0.0676
C2	2.47	2.90	-0.43	0.06	0.1849	0.0036

C3	2.24	2.99	-0.66	0.15	0.4356	0.0225
C4	2.75	2.51	-0.15	-0.33	0.0225	0.1089
C5	2.90	2.58	0.00	-0.26	0.0000	0.0676
C6	2.65	2.76	-0.25	-0.08	0.0625	0.0064
C7	3.07	2.39	0.17	-0.45	0.0289	0.2025
C8	3.04	3.00	0.14	0.16	0.0196	0.0256
C9	3.29	2.82	0.39	-0.02	0.1521	0.0004
C10	2.77	2.91	-0.13	0.07	0.0169	0.0049
C11	3.12	2.83	0.22	-0.01	0.0484	0.0001
C12	3.02	2.98	0.12	0.14	0.0144	0.0196
C13	3.13	3.31	0.23	0.47	0.0529	0.2209
C14	3.09	3.44	0.19	0.60	0.0361	0.3600
C15	3.15	2.53	0.25	-0.31	0.0625	0.0961
	$\sum Y_E = 43.46$	$\sum Y_M = 42.53$			$\sum (Y_E - \bar{Y}_E)^2 = 1.1541$	$\sum (Y_M - \bar{Y}_M)^2 = 1.2067$

$$\bar{Y}_E = \sum Y_E / N = 43.46 / 15 = 2.90$$

$$\bar{Y}_M = \sum Y_M / N = 42.53 / 15 = 2.84$$

$$S_E^2 = \sum (Y_E - \bar{Y}_E)^2 / (N-1) = 1.1541 / 14 = 0.0824$$

$$S_M^2 = \sum (Y_M - \bar{Y}_M)^2 / (N-1) = 1.2067 / 14 = 0.0862$$

Therefore, $S_1^2 = 0.0862$ and $S_2^2 = 0.0824$

$$F_{\text{calculated}} = S_1^2 / S_2^2 = 0.0862 / 0.0824 = 1.05$$

$$F_{\text{table}} = F_{0.05}(14,14)$$

From statistical table for F-distribution values, $F_{0.05}(14,14) = 2.48$

$$1/F_{\text{table}} = 0.403$$

Therefore, $0.403 < 1.05 < 2.48$

Thus, the condition $1/F < S_1^2 / S_2^2 < F$ has been satisfied. Null hypothesis will be accepted.

CONCLUSION

From the statistical analysis carried out on the generated regression model for the prediction of flexural strengths of concrete made with periwinkle shells and river gravel, blended as a single component at a volumetric mix ratio of 1:1, the calculated f-value of 1.05 was less than the allowable f-value of 2.48 from the statistical table at 5% significance level. This means that the flexural strengths results from the experiment and those from the model compare favourably with each other. It can therefore be concluded that the regression model proved adequate for the prediction of 28th-day flexural strengths of concrete made from equal volume of river gravel and periwinkle shells at 95% confidence level or 5% significance level. This model is recommended for use in concrete industry or construction industry for easy forecast of flexural strengths of lightweight concretes whose mix ratios are within the boundaries provided in this research work.

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